

Review

A study on some advanced applications of Electrostatics

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Abstract: Physicists deal with the four fundamental forces: gravitational force, weak nuclear force, strong nuclear force, and electromagnetic force. Electrostatics is the subfield of Electromagnetics describing attractive or repulsive forces between particles that are caused by their electric charges. It's the study of electromagnetic occurrences that takes place while a static equilibrium has been established. Charges reach their equilibrium situations swiftly for the reason that the electric force is exceedingly sturdy. Electrostatics in its most obstructive sense is a modification of Maxwell's equations to a system whose foundations are steady-state, time-invariant electric charges

Keywords: Electromagnetics, electromagnetic force, electric energy

Introduction

Ever wondered how lightning occurs? Or why a spark can be seen when removing sweater in a dark room? Electrostatics can help explain these amazing natural phenomena. The phenomena of electrostatic charge is everlasting and is generated principally by relative movement - in other words every time material exteriors have contact and are separated or have friction with each other. Static electricity is an accustomed electric occurrence wherein charged atoms are transported from one physique to another The phenomena of electrostatic is resulted by attraction of charges to each other. Let's say, if two substances are rubbed together, specifically if the substances are insulators and the adjoining environment is arid, the substances attain equivalent and conflicting charges and a magnetic power grows among them. The object that loses electrons befits positively charged, and the other turned out to be negatively charged. The force is basically the attraction among charges of opposite sign. This is the most fundamental theory of electrostatics. The possessions of

this force were described above, they are combined in the mathematical affiliation known as Coulomb's law. Although the forces where paper snippets are attracted by a CD-ROM might look very small, the electrostatic force is in appraisal with the gravitational force extremely strong. The force between an Electron and a Proton (both are building a hydrogen atom) is about 40 times larger in comparison to the gravitational force between the both.

Basically the electrostatics deals with quiescent electric loads, load distributions and the electric fields of loaded objects.

Applications of Electrostatics:

Electrostatics has many examples that can be seen in real life. Lightning amongst them is the most common natural phenomena. Influence machines and Friction machines like *The Van de Graaff Generator* ^[1] is a spectacular device used to demonstrate high voltage due to static electricity. In this paper we are going to discuss a few of these applications of electrostatics and electrostatic force.

Electrostatic beneficiation of fly ash: Electrostatic separation is in practice of beneficiating minerals since the early 20th century (Ralston, 1961). The advantages of electrostatic separation for separating unburned carbon from fly ash to produce a concrete quality pozzolana are many when compared to wet beneficiation processes or combustion-based thermal processes. Electrostatic separation is a dry process that involves no water, and the recovered ash product does not require dewatering and drying. The process also does not generate wastewater contaminated with flotation chemicals. Furthermore requires very little energy. The unburned carbon separated from the raw feed ash is returned to the utility boiler to recover the fuel value. This electrostatic process does not generate combustion-related pollutants, such as nitrogen oxides, sulfur oxides, or mercury. ^[2]

Spray Painting: Electrostatic spraying also known as powder coating is an ideal technique for painting wire fence, angles, channels, cables, and pipes. It includes imparting the material with electrical charge (up to 60,000 volts) of opposite potential to the surface to be painted, causing the charged particles to be attracted to the surface. ^[3] Particles of paint are set positive charge as they leave the nozzle of a spray gun. The object to be painted is earthed so that there is an electric field between the nozzle and the object. Car body panels and bike frames are two examples where electrostatic spray painting is often used.

Electrostatic Precipitator: Electrostatic forces are effective for subtraction of contaminant particles on surfaces and for manipulation and transport of micro- and nanoscale particles. Subtraction of particles depends on overpowering the adhesion forces of the particle to the surface. [4] Tiny particles of soot, ash, and dust are major components of the airborne emissions from fossil fuel-burning power plants and from many industrial processing plants. Electrostatic precipitators can remove nearly all of these particles from the emissions. [5]

Micro actuators design and technology: Electrostatic forces are commonly witnessed in the macroscopic domain. Such energy has been successfully harnessed in micro actuators and it is the most frequently applied actuation due to its versatility, simplicity and high compatibility with IC fabrication technology. No special materials – for example, piezoelectric ceramics, or additional elements such as coils – are required, therefore eliminating some of the cost inefficient assembly process. The concept of electrostatic energy is convenient when calculating electrostatic forces and capacitance values. [6]

Electrostatics in Biomolecules: Electrostatics plays a central role in determining the structures and functions of biomolecules. All living organisms contain either DNA or RNA. These molecules contain genetic information that defines (or at least influences) all of the organism's characteristics. DNA is a large macromolecule that (in three-dimensional space) forms the shape of a double helix. [7] The backbone of each and every helix is formed from alternating deoxyribose and phosphate subunits. Each deoxyribose is linked to a base that extends between the two backbones. Four bases can be found in DNA: adenine, guanine, cytosine and thymine. Their ordering in sequence determines the genetic characteristics of the parent organism. The bases of each strand of DNA are positioned close to one another but not as a result of formal chemical bonds. Electrostatic interactions, in this case otherwise known as hydrogen bonds, are what hold these bonds together. [8]

Photocopy Machines and Printers: Photocopiers use xerography, a procedure that uses principles of electrostatics, to duplicate images. Diverse models of photocopiers vary somewhat in their approaches, but the first instance of xerography involved use of a photo sensor with a copy camera and a separate processing unit. Till now, xerography is conducted in a five-step process, in which electrostatics play an important role. [9]

Surface and Colloid Chemistry: Electrostatic forces are solitary existing where charged particles act together through a polar medium. Thus, electrostatic forces are particularly significant for

ceramic materials in polar medium such as water or ethanol. The electrostatic forces are in general stronger and longer range than all other surface forces. Therefore, they often dominate the properties of a colloidal suspension. The surface reactions that leads to surface charge consisting the charged particle and its surrounding liquid is electrically neutral. [10]

Electrostatics in Enzyme: While the purpose and mechanism of enzymes has been well-known to researchers for decades, the driving force behind it is still a hotly debated topic. Herein, Quantum Computations report significant evidence for electrostatics being that driving force, using a simple, computationally inexpensive, multiscale model of monoamine oxidase and phenyl ethylamine. They found that electrostatics provided by the enzyme substantially enhances the reaction by all the considered criteria. [11]

Vessel Regeneration and Bioengineering: Electrostatic cell seeding refers to cell seeding via manipulation of the electrostatic properties of vascular scaffolds. This is consummated by inducing a temporary positive surface charge on the luminal surface of an ePTFE scaffold in order to enhance negatively charged EC adhesion. Research has demonstrated that the utilization of this method for as little as 16 min results in seeding efficiencies of up to 90%. Magnetic cell seeding techniques involve the use of magnetic forces to increase cell seeding efficiency. The rudimentary principle relies on the use of a magnet to attract nanoparticles attached to the surface or inside of seeded cells. The advantages of these techniques include short duration, seeding efficiency up to 90% and reproducible results, all of which are essential for constructing grafts for clinical applications. [12]

Electrostatics in Electronics: Ordinary electrostatic phenomena are utmost acquainted as an infrequent irritation in times of truncated moisture, but can be critical and hurtful in some states.

When waged in uninterrupted interaction with combined circuit electronics (especially delicate MOSFETs), or in the existence of flammable gas, precaution must be taken to evade accumulating and abruptly discharging a static charge. [13]

Computer Assisted Drug Design: Electrostatic interactions play a significant role in ligand–receptor binding. They are long-range, varying with distance

as r^{-1} , and therefore can be particularly important for molecular recognition. Each molecule can

be considered to have not only a net charge but also a charge distribution over the whole molecule. In modeling studies of ligand–receptor binding, partial charges are usually assigned to atom centers on the basis of ab initio or semi empirical quantum mechanical calculations or simpler approaches such as electronegativity equalization. Like charges repel and unlike charges attract. Consequently, many positive and negative terms contribute to the coulombic electrostatic energy of a ligand–receptor complex. Electrostatic interactions can be exploited in drug design. An example is provided by the anti-influenza drug Relenza. This compound is an inhibitor of the neuraminidase coat protein of the influenza virus. The design was to modify a transition state analog on the basis of the crystal structure of the enzyme so as to optimize binding affinity. By probing the protein with different probes with the GRID program an interfacial pocket was identified where a positively charged amino or guanidine group could favorably be added as a substituent to the transition state analog. Compounds with these positively charged substituents turned out to be very potent and one of them, Relenza, is used in the clinic. It is delivered to its site of action as a nasal spray: its charged functional groups make it too polar for oral delivery, which requires the compound to be able to pass through membranes.

Conclusion

Electrostatics is an elaborate yet interesting part of theoretical physics. It has picked people's interested since Benjamin Franklin's famous kite experiment in 1752. The mayhem continues till now not only in field of Physics but in Chemistry, Neuro Science, Material Science, Molecular Biology and the list goes on. Connections between electrostatics and other fields are making epic achievements understanding the way atomic domain works more and more. Electrostatics and the study of static electricity is often seem as child's play whilst this is a serious issue and important key factor as an industrial level.

References

- [1] <https://www.texasgateway.org/resource/17-applications-electrostatics>
- [2] J.D. Bittner, F.J. Hrach, in Coal Combustion Products (CCP's), 2017
- [3] Alireza Bahadori Ph.D., in Essentials of Coating, Painting, and Lining for the Oil, Gas and Petrochemical Industries, 2015
- [4] Rajiv Kohli, in Developments in Surface Contamination and Cleaning: Applications of Cleaning Techniques, 2019

- [5] <https://www.miniphysics.com/applications-of-electrostatics.html>
- [6] L. Li, Z.J. Chew, in Smart Sensors and Mems, 2014
- [7] [https://phys.libretexts.org/Bookshelves/University_Physics/Book%3A_Physics_\(Bouundles\)/17%3A_Electric_Charge_and_Field/17.6%3A_Applications_of_Electrostatics](https://phys.libretexts.org/Bookshelves/University_Physics/Book%3A_Physics_(Bouundles)/17%3A_Electric_Charge_and_Field/17.6%3A_Applications_of_Electrostatics)
- [8] Qin Cai, Ray Luo, in Annual Reports in Computational Chemistry, 2012
- [9] https://www.hildebrand-technology.com/en/know_how/electrostatic/
- [10] J.H. Adair, J. Sindel, in Materials: Science and Technology, 2001
- [11] Alja Prah, Janez Marvi, Jarnej Stare in Electrostatics as the Driving Force Behind the Catalytic Function of the Monoamine Oxidase, A Enzyme Confirmed by Quantum Computations, 2019
- [12] Shuhei Tara, Christopher K. Breuer, in Regenerative Medicine Applications in Organ Transplantation, 2014
- [13] <https://courses.lumenlearning.com/physics/chapter/18-8-applications-of-electrostatics/>

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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